

Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency

Simran Ahuja

BBA., L.L.B. (Hons), Indore Institute of Law, Affiliated To DAVV and BCI,
Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Prevention of juvenile delinquency mainly focus on the most effectual way to prevent juvenile delinquency, it has indisputably been to provide counselling and proper guidance to children and their families at a premature stage. Several state programme attempt early intervention and prevention and independent groups in communities have taken initiatives to tackle the problem in new ways. Some basic steps that should be taken to prevent child delinquency include increasing the awareness among parents. First of all, it is important to identify such children that are involved in a conflict with the law and then try to give them a proper treatment. The treatment should be given on a regular basis so that these children will not become habitual to commit such offences. The main cause for the involvement of children in committing a crime is due to the surroundings they live in. It is said that child is so innocent to follow the things they learn at their early stage. If the proper education is provided at their early stage, it will decrease the number of offences committed by the child. Efforts to prevent juvenile delinquency have a long history, but generally, they have not been subjected to scientific evaluation of their effects.

INTRODUCTION

Young persons who are charged with crimes are treated as a juvenile if he or she is below the age of 18 years. These juvenile cases are known as juvenile delinquency. In order to put off juvenile delinquents, we have to deal not only with youths who are caught up in conflict with the law but also with those children who are creating discord in schools and in the streets while not violating the laws

Children are the foundation on which the vibrant future of a nation shall be built. They are the greatest asset for the nation. The delicate mind of a child can be moulded very easily and can turn them towards the criminal activities. This has now turned out to be the most debateable issue for the society. Prevention is necessary for such children. If they are not prevented they will end up becoming a habitual offender.

The word delinquency is derived from the Latin term 'delinquere' which means to abandon. Now here is a big confusion between a juvenile and a minor, these two are very different terms. A young criminal offender is referred as a juvenile and minor is a term used to denote or relate with someone's legal capacity. Nowadays, a government has recognized the importance of preventing delinquency at an earlier stage and therefore it has started allocating cremation, funds and resources for its prevention. As an improvement of delinquency youth is being influenced by various factors, so there has to be a comprehensive approach in preventing it. Prevention service includes activities such as education and treatment regarding substance exploitation, youth mentoring programmes, parenting education, emotional support, family counselling and youth encouragement in different fields.

PREVENTIVE PROGRAMMES OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

Individual programme –

1. **Clinical programme** –through the clinical programme, many psychologists and psychiatric social workers are employed and they go to a different area as assigned to them for understanding the mentality and personality

disorder of juvenile delinquents and to provide them with the best counselling.

2. **Educational curriculum and activities** – the result of education is remarkable in the nation where the school going children ratio is very high. Preventive measures can be taken in this area, where participation of teachers will also play roles by not discriminating children, teaching moral values, which is important for the mental development of growing child which also is the basis for their future life.
3. **Mental hygiene** – this also has a major role in preventing juvenile delinquency. Curing psychological disorder, mental disturbance, and mental conflicts and thus bringing ample mental regulation in childhood.
4. **Parent education**—parental education is very essential for the juvenile from preventing them from being involved in crimes.

ENVIRONMENTAL PROGRAMMES

1. **Community programme**—the term community is a group of people, who live in a particular area and have an interest in each other for the purpose of making a living. The main purpose of the community programme is to get in contact with the individual in need of help instead of someone who himself approaches the workers and prepared to take participation in the local community programme. It is an initiative to bring people together and acknowledge them about the preventive steps that could be taken in this matter.
2. **Publication**- If journalists, media or another sort of publicity is given to the juvenile delinquent the physiotherapy and psychotherapy will become more complicated. Lesser the exposure in the individual case increases the odds of a delinquent youngster to get back to his normal social life thus preventing him from social stigma.
3. **Parental care, love and affection**- the bond between children and parents are created because of parents love care and affection. Children need unconditional love care and fondness for his/her parents. The child may develop irritation, frustration and disappointment in their mind due to lack of knowledge and ignorance of such care and protection which might lead them towards offences and felony.

ROLE OF POLICE

Children are the fragile section of the society. They should be treated with due care and protection, when a

child commits a crime he or she should be given sympathetic treatment, it is the duty of the police to investigate into the matter of child and decide whether the child should be provided under the custody of juvenile justice board or should be taken under the custody of police itself. The police, while dealing with the child consider the facts, circumstances and the nature of the offence to decide whether the child should be sent to the juvenile justice board or in police custody. In India police plays a major role to look after the child from any sought of injury or damage. Police are responsible for maintaining the law and order in the society. it is the obligation to the police to investigate the different area where crimes are being held so that the child should be prevented from indulging in such criminal activities. The main function of the police is to arrest or detain a child who is involved in such activities.

PROBLEMS IN ADMINISTRATION OF JUSTICE

The main problem faced by juveniles in India is due to the bad administration of the justice system. Although there are many states in India but not every state has a juvenile justice board established there. Due to the scarcity of juvenile courts, a numerous number of problems are being faced by children in India. In order to cover up this particular problem, juvenile justice board had granted some powers to the different authorities. These authorities do not have a proper knowledge about the law related to the child. They are not specialized in this field and thus child faces various problems. This indicates the need to create more juvenile justice boards that have a special knowledge about the law related to the child.

SPECIAL JUVENILE AID POLICE

India is the second most populated country in the world, with varieties of culture, tradition and customs. The people residing in India follow different standards of living and they have their own ways to tackle the problems faced by them. Especially in urban areas, the quantum is very high in comparison to rural areas. The trained police are easily available in urban areas but in a rural area, the police are not that much trained. For example, in Bombay, the first juvenile aid police unit was established in October 1952, as a part of an observation branch which is under the control of D.C.P and the head must be a lady inspector. Here, the police basically deal with the cases related victimised children and they hold a duty to enforce the provisions of Bombay children act. For

those boys who ran away from their houses and found on railway stations, Bombay railway juvenile guide service was established.

A study was conducted by the juvenile aid police unit where it has suggested that in highly populated areas, the special trained officers should be kept so that they could look after the crimes and offences committed there. It has also suggested solving the problem of involvement of a child in consuming drugs and other chemical substances by way of counselling. They have also recommended preparing a particular team of the specialized officer who would supervise and guide the city police in dealing with such kinds of matters.

SPECIAL TRAINING TO POLICE

In big cities like Bombay, Chennai, Delhi and Bangalore, the police should have a good behaviour towards the child. While dealing with the child at their level, they should make sure that they know about the child psychology and behaviour. Children are very weak and innocent part of society and thus they should be treated tenderly. Special training should be given to the police to encounter the child so that they should be able to learn about the nature and manners of the child.

SOCIALIZATION OF POLICE

- 1. Juvenile's impression towards the police:** A survey was conducted in Burdwan regarding the approach of the high school boys towards Indian police which stated the boys have a different mentality towards the police; they look upon the police as an aggressive and violent person. Not more than 2% of boys had a feeling that the police is acting as a friend. More than 60% of the boys think that police is very furious while dealing with them and the remaining boys do not have any idea.
- 2. Police as a preventive force:** before punishing the criminal, the police is primarily responsible to prevent the crime from being conducted by any criminal. It has the duty to maintain the law and order in the society and this it should work towards the prevention of crime.
- 3. Police approach towards the Juvenile:** The police should change its attitude towards the

Juvenile. They should give proper treatment to the child. Children are very tender and thus they should be treated with sympathy. The police should treat them with respect and in a friendly manner rather than being aggressive.

- 4. Maintenance of record of history sheets:** If the records of the crimes committed by the child are maintained, it will have two effects. First of all, the Positive effect will be it will help in maintaining the record so that after he or she had become adult and committed any crime, these records can be taken as the evidence of his or her criminal history. While on the other hand, it has a negative aspect as well, the maintenance of such records of the child would be a stigma on him and would affect his future. Although, according to the juvenile justice board (2000), the records should be destroyed within 7 years of the crime.

REHABILITATION OF RELEASED JUVENILE:

The treatment of a child is different from adults. If a child commits any crime, the main focus is to rehabilitate the child rather than punishing him. Rehabilitation is the process where the child is provided with expert advice to deal with the situations. He is given proper guidance to tackle the circumstances. The child is provided with expert training under the supervision of different authorities as stated by the court orders. He is also provided with the probation officer for some time after being rehabilitated. The main purpose behind this is to keep an eye upon the child to prevent him from doing any further crime. Various programs based on communities are held to spread awareness and to prevent the further commencement of such crimes. The preventive programs can be classified into pure or primary prevention and rehabilitative or secondary prevention. The pure or primary prevention focuses on preventing the child from committing the crime before he or she has committed any crime and have been adjudicated for the same. While the rehabilitative or secondary prevention focuses on preventing the child to commit any crime after he or she been adjudicated so that he or she should be more aware in the future.